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Protein: Structure and Function

Oksana Mandal, Kaveri Vishwas Sable and Lenin Kumar Bompalli

Introduction

Proteins are one of the most abundant organic molecules in living systems and have the most diverse range of functions of all macromolecules. Proteins are highly complex macromolecules consisting of one or more long chains of amino acids linked together by peptide bonds. Proteins may be structural, regulatory, contractile, or protective. They may serve in transport, storage, or membranes; or they may be toxins or enzymes. Each cell in a living system may contain thousands of proteins, each with a unique function. Their structures, like their functions, vary greatly. They are all, however, amino acid polymers arranged in a linear sequence (also referred to as a “peptide”). Proteins are coded and regulated by genes. These proteins, along with the environment, cause an organism’s traits. Muscle mass. It is commonly found in animal products, though Protein is a macro nutrient that is essential to building is also present in other sources, such as nuts & legumes. There are 20 different types of Amino Acids that are combined to make a protein. These amino acids are attached to each other by the peptide bond, which forms between the carboxyl group of first amino acid and amide group of second amino

acid. The traditional hunter-gather diets eaten by our pre-agricultural ancestors were higher in animal protein than contemporary diet (Konner and Eaton, 2010).

History

Proteins were first described by the Dutch chemist Mulder and named by Swedish chemist Berzelius in 1838. Proteins were recognized as a distinct class of biological molecules in the 18th century by Antoine and others, distinguished by the molecules ability to coagulate or flocculate under treatments with heat or acid. At the time noted examples included Albumin from Egg whites, Blood serum albumin, Fibrin and Wheat gluten. Mulder carried out elemental analysis of common proteins and found that nearly all protein had same empirical formula, $C_{400}H_{620}N_{100}O_{120}P_1S_1$.

Properties of Proteins

- ✓ Proteins may be either tasteless (tyrosine), sweet (glycine and alanine) or bitter (arginine).
- ✓ They have high melting point.
- ✓ They are soluble in polar solvents like Water and Ethanol but they are insoluble in nonpolar solvents such as Benzene and Ether.
- ✓ The solubility in water is dependent on pH and

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on salt concentration.

- ✓ Water interacts with polar groups of proteins and forms an aqueous membrane- hydration shell-at the surface of the protein.
- ✓ The optical activity of proteins is due not only to asymmetry of amino acids but also to the chirality resulting from the arrangement of the peptide chain.

Roles of proteins

- ✓ Protein acts as enzymes and hormones i.e., Insulin, Glycogen.
- ✓ It provides nutrients transport and making antibodies i.e., Haemoglobin.
- ✓ It provides energy when carbohydrates and fat intake is inadequate.
- ✓ A class of protein known as fibrous proteins provide various part of our body with structure, strength and elasticity.
- ✓ Various protein hormones regulate the growth of plants and animals besides controlling many other physiological functions.
- ✓ The nucleoproteins serve as carrier of genetics characters and hence govern inheritance of traits. Proteins act as a buffer system, helping our body maintain proper pH values of blood and other bodily fluids.
- ✓ High-protein diets may influence energy balance by increasing post-meal satiety and increasing basal energy expenditures (Westerterp-Plantenga *et al.*, 2009).

Structure of Proteins

Protein structure is the three-dimensional

arrangement of atoms in a protein. There are thousands of proteins in each cell in a living system, each with a unique function and structure. The unique structures of proteins determine their functions. Understanding the structure of proteins is important as it reveals the mechanism involved in various cellular processes.

Basics of Protein Structure

Amino acids are the fundamental building elements of proteins. These are organic compounds with a carboxyl group, an amino group, a core carbon atom, and a characteristic side chain. Peptide bonds hold these amino acids together to build lengthy protein chains. In this chain, there are two ends: the starting point is called the amino terminus (N-terminus), and the ending point is called the carboxyl terminus (C-terminus). Proteins are built from only twenty amino acids, each with a distinct side chain. The side chains of amino acids vary in their characteristics. The peculiarities of the side chains significantly influence how the protein behaves. The protein prefers acidic or basic environments because some of its side chains have these properties.

Levels of Protein Structure: Proteins can be divided into four structural levels: primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary structures, depending on the level of their structure.

Primary Structure of Protein

The linear sequence of amino acids connected by peptide bonds is known as the primary structure, and it represents the earliest level of protein structure. Peptide and disulfide bonding pres-

erve the core structure. The precise sequence in which the genetic code is read from the relevant gene determines the basic structure of a protein. The characteristics of specific amino acids in the primary structure influence how the proteins fold at the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary levels e.g. Albumin, Histones etc.

Secondary Structure of Protein

The precise spatial arrangement of a given peptide sequence is known as the secondary structure of a protein. It describes the particular arrangement of amino acid residues in a polypeptide chain, where they are grouped closely together. This arrangement takes place in specific locations where the chain folds locally to create the protein's secondary structure. The two most common secondary structures of proteins are alpha-helix and beta-pleated sheets e.g. Collagen etc.

Tertiary Structure of Protein

The tertiary structure of a protein refers to the three-dimensional arrangement of all atoms of a protein formed after the polypeptide chain folds and twists further. This arrangement is determined by the interactions of side chains of the polypeptide backbone. The tertiary structure of a protein is stabilized by five types of interactions: hydrophobic interaction, ionic interaction, hydrogen bond, Vanderwaal's interaction, and disulfide bond. A protein may contain one or several unique domains connected by loop regions. These domains usually contain 100-200 amino acid residues and contribute to both functional as well as structural properties of

the protein e.g. Myoglobin, Keratin etc.

Quaternary Structure of Protein

Quaternary structure is the fourth degree of structural organization seen in proteins with multiple polypeptide chains. In these proteins, every polypeptide chain is referred to as a subunit. The spatial arrangement of these subunits and their interactions are referred to as quaternary structure. The most basic type of quaternary structure consists of a dimer, which is made up of two identical subunits. More intricate quaternary structures are, nevertheless, also typical. The quaternary structure is formed from the interactions between the side chains of two or more polypeptides and affects the overall shape of the protein e.g. Hemoglobin etc.

Methods for studying protein structure

- ✓ **X-ray crystallography:** it is one of the commonly used methods to determine protein structures. It involves crystallizing the protein and exposing it to X-rays. The diffracted X-ray pattern is analyzed to create an electron density map, which is then interpreted to locate each atom in the protein. This method provides detailed atomic information about proteins and

other molecules in the crystal.

- ✓ **NMR spectroscopy:** An additional valuable technique for researching protein structures is NMR spectroscopy. It entails putting pure proteins in a magnetic field and using radio waves to probe them. A model of the protein's structure is created using the information about atom conformation that the ensuing resonances provide. Unlike other techniques that call for crystallization, NMR is useful for examining flexible proteins in solution.
- ✓ **Homology modeling:** It is one such computational method used to predict the three-dimensional structure of a protein. It relies on a known protein structure (a template) that is closely related to the protein being studied.

Conclusion

Proteins are nitrogenous organic compounds of high molecular weight which play a vital or prime role in living organisms. They are made up of 20 standard α -amino acids. They serve as body building units, e.g., muscle proteins. Proteins are one of the

most abundant organic molecules in living systems and have the most diverse range of functions of all macromolecules.

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